

IMPACT OF CAREER COUNSELING TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES ON CAREER DECISION MAKING DIFFICULTIES OF STUDENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Career counselling and guidance is a lifelong process. It is an inherent part of education at Schools. Career counselling doesn't mean prescribing set of jobs or courses that lead to it. It is a process that enables students to know their interests, skills, strengths and weaknesses, so that they make an informed choice of their careers and life goals. Guidance shall go beyond curriculum. Having repeated discussions with students on diverse range of issues such as time management, concentration levels, reading-writing and analytical skills, disagreement issues between student and parents is part of guidance. This study is conducted to know whether this sort of career counselling and guidance is being given in schools, how far students are aware of it and are ready. Students face many issues at adolescent age (17, 18 years of age). At this age they have to make wise decision regarding courses to be taken in under graduation and future careers. Hence sampling units are students studying 11th, 12th grades. A reasonable study has been undertaken to assess career awareness of school passed out students, sort of guidance provided by teachers and the atmosphere fostered by top management. Quantitative analysis was conducted to analyse pretest and posttest outcomes. This study is experimental and empirical in nature. The present study is unique as it explored various career decision making difficulties, addressed them with psychometric tests and sessions. Such an empirical study was made to know effectiveness of those tools in assisting career counselling process.

INTRODUCTION

Case.1: "This is not what I am interested to study, but forced by my parents".

Case 2: "I have studied mechanical engineering, but situations forced to become software engineer."

Case 3: "I wanted to become a district collector, but don't know what to study and how to go forward"

All the above cases are real encounters but similar to those also occur very frequently. When a 11th or 12th grader is forced to take up a subject which she/he doesn't like or which is beyond her/his capacity alienation occurs. Unable to resist parent's force, lack of awareness regarding their interests and career opportunities, they are forced to take up subjects in under graduation. Initially they struggle a lot, but gradually realize that they cannot cope up with subjects and syllabus.

Finally, many students go into depression and they become alienated with themselves... In such situations to know one's own interests, abilities and careers that match to both of these, career counselling and guidance in a correct way at the correct time is the solution.

Education is the process of facilitating learning and the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Education is the passport to the future, for tomorrow belongs to those who prepare for it today. In today's globalised world, there are wide ranges of courses, jobs that are available across the globe.

But students who just entered 11th or 12th are not completely aware of those opportunities. Sometimes, even when they wish to pursue some course, parents don't agree. Parents and schools feel that students are not mature enough to take decision.

This stage is called +1, +2 in some states. This is called as 11th and 12th and is inherent part of schools as extension of schools. But in some states like Andhra Pradesh, it is called as Intermediate. It is called with different names in different states of India.

But this stage, before they enter under graduation and college is very crucial as that is the point where they have to decide on their future course of action. Lack of awareness regarding colleges/ courses, lack of self-analysis will lead to wrong choices and mismatched careers. Hence career counselling by a trained, certified professional career counsellor answers all these issues.

Career counsellor guides anyone irrespective of age to help him direct his life, develop his own point of view, make his own informed decisions and carry out his own personal and professional life as per his interest. It does not dictate choices for an individual. It helps to develop his abilities in such a way that he can make choices independently with the inputs given by counsellor.

It involves all the services that contribute in self-understanding of an individual and his personal and social requirements to take decision about future. To know interests, aptitude, suitable careers for personality types many psychometric assessment tests are used. These serve as tools for career counsellors. There are various standard theories based on which these tools are constructed.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK OF VARIOUS TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES USED IN CAREER COUNSELING

- MBTI – Myer Briggs Type Indicator

The Myers- Briggs Type Indicator consists of 16 combinations, eight preferences organized into four dyads of contraries. MBTI personality type represents individual natural preferences in four important aspects of personality.

People will have inch or much of all of these but they utmost prefer one side of a preference further than the other which accounts for the natural personality differences among people.

16 Myers-Briggs Personality Types

<p>INTJ Innovative, independent, strategic, logical, reserved, insightful. Driven by original ideas to achieve improvements.</p>	<p>INTP Intellectual, logical, precise, reserved, flexible, imaginative. Thinkers who enjoy speculation & creative problem solving.</p>	<p>ENTJ Strategic, logical, efficient, outgoing, ambitious, independent. Effective organizers of people and planners.</p>	<p>ENTP Inventive, enthusiastic, strategic, enterprising, inquisitive, versatile. Enjoy new ideas and challenges, value inspiration.</p>
<p>INFJ Idealistic, organized, insightful, dependable, compassionate, gentle. Peace & cooperation.</p>	<p>INFP Sensitive, creative, idealistic, perceptive, caring, loyal. Harmony and growth, dreams and possibilities.</p>	<p>ENFJ Caring, enthusiastic, idealistic, organized, diplomatic, responsible. Skilled communicators who value connection</p>	<p>ENFP Enthusiastic, creative, spontaneous, optimistic, supportive, playful. Inspiration, new projects, see potential.</p>
<p>ISTJ Responsible, sincere, analytical, reserved, realistic, systematic. Hardworking and trustworthy with practical judgement.</p>	<p>ISFJ Warm, considerate, gentle, responsible, pragmatic, thorough. Devoted caretakers who enjoy being helpful to others.</p>	<p>ESTJ Efficient, outgoing, analytical, systematic, dependable, realistic. Like to run the show and get things done in an orderly fashion.</p>	<p>ESFJ Friendly, outgoing, reliable, conscientious, organized, practical. Helpful and please others, enjoy being active and productive.</p>
<p>ISTP Action-oriented, logical, analytical, spontaneous, reserved, independent. Enjoy adventure, skilled at understanding things.</p>	<p>ISFP Gentle, sensitive, nurturing, helpful, flexible, realistic. Personal environment is beautiful & practical.</p>	<p>ESTP Outgoing, realistic, action-oriented, curious, versatile, spontaneous. Pragmatic problem solvers & negotiators.</p>	<p>ESFP Playful, enthusiastic, friendly, spontaneous, tactful, flexible. Have common sense, enjoy helping people.</p>

Source: <https://www.earlyyears.tv/myers-briggs-personality-types-complete-guide/>

- Holland Codes

RIASEC is the hexagon which categorises people on one or two of the above.

- Strong Interest Inventory

This was developed by Edward Strong. It is used to determine interests of candidates towards various careers. It has around 291 items but widely narrowing to six areas. It takes into consideration values that individual gives importance at workplace and interests. It also compares candidate interests with available professions and gives output.

- 16 PF

Sixteen personality factor test was modelled on Cattell's theory. It has been revamped many times with several additions. Design of questions was based on Likert scale.

Cattell's sixteen Factors of Personality (16PF)									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
Reserved									Outgoing
Less intelligent									More intelligent
Affected by feelings									Emotionally Stable
Submissive									Dominant
Serious									Happy-go-lucky
Expedient									Conscientious
Timid									Venturesome
Tough-minded									Sensitive
Trusting									Suspicious
Practical									Imaginative
Forthright									Shrewd
Self-assured									Apprehensive
Conservative									Experimenting
Group dependent									Self-sufficient
Uncontrolled									Controlled
Relaxed									Tense

Source: google generated

Based on options selected by students, it will generate a result.

Factor		Descriptors	
A	Warmth	Reserved	Outgoing
B	Reasoning	Less Intelligent	More Intelligent
C	Emotional Stability	Affected by feelings	Emotionally stable
E	Dominance	Humble	Assertive
F	Liveliness	Sober	Happy-go-lucky
G	Rule Consciousness	Expedient	Conscientious
H	Social Boldness	Shy	Venturesome
I	Sensitivity	Tough-minded	Tender-minded
L	Vigilance	Trusting	Suspicious
M	Abstractedness	Practical	Imaginative
N	Privateness	Straightforward	Shrewd
O	Apprehension	Self-Assured	Apprehensive
Q1	Openness to Change	Conservative	Experimenting
Q2	Self-Reliance	Group-dependent	Self-sufficient
Q3	Perfectionism	Self-conflict	Self-control
Q4	Tension	Relaxed	Tense

Similarly, the other elements of PM can be defined as following formal expression.
Study Motivation Information of Learner:

NEED OF THE STUDY

In a new era of disruption, many technologies change all the fields. Students need to get equipped with such an education and skills. They have to be aware of different courses to take up such careers as per their interests and abilities. Many developed nations like USA, UK, Germany, Canada, etc are implementing career counselling to give students all the above guidance. But India is not yet implementing career counselling at each and every school. Hence it is highly needed to study career decision making difficulties, how they can be addressed with psychometric tests and how these tools aid counsellors.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is limited to students only. Also, it applies only to 11th and 12th graders. It is limited to few colleges in Andhra Pradesh, India. Psychometric tests are conducted only in colleges that are equipped with necessary computers, network.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ahmad Oweini and Rania Abdo (2000), in their study An Experimental Career Counseling Workshop for Lebanese Secondary School Students conducted career counselling sessions and analysed response. Researchers felt career counselling has long been neglected in Lebanon. Hence career counselling sessions are conducted in Beirut for 116 students. A preliminary questionnaire was given to know how far students know about their own choices, skills, career goals.

Then a session was conducted. Later Holland code based psychometric assessment test was conducted. Post counselling, questionnaire was given. Researchers observed students at high school stage are facing lot of confusions. During that stage they have to choose their majors of education, career. But preliminary questionnaire has shown majority of the students do not have a clear idea of how to choose careers and about their own skills. As per Holland theory there are 6 kinds of personalities groups: Realistic (R), Investigative (I), Artistic (A), Social (S), Enterprising (E) RIASEC. Test that is constructed based on this, generates code based on answers given by students. College Majors Finder was conducted to know college majors which matches to Holland code. These tools were used in career counselling to guide students. More than half of the students were never exposed to such sort of career counselling workshop. 60% of them who doesn't have clarity on future career are now clear about their goals. 55% of them who are unaware of education majors are sure about their colleges and education majors. 95% opined that the workshop was very useful and an eye opener. Even the top management was ready to implement such programs with trained professional counsellors.

Lynn Merlone (2005), in her study Record Keeping and the School Counselor studied how middle school counsellors are storing student information and sticking on to protocols. The researcher selected 14 school counsellors and conducted in depth interviews. After an extensive study she chose American School Counselors association (ASCA) standards to store, disseminate, destruct information with counsellor. Confidentiality is the prime factor under ethics policy of counselling. There are many states laws on how to maintain information and what is considered breach. The main objectives were to know how counsellors are documenting their work, what sort of daily planners, log books or record books are used in hard copy or soft copy? What information is the school giving? What is gathered from parents? How many months or years do a counsellor keep permanent record of a particular student? She came to know that once students pass out and opt for a particular university, they normally destroy the information. Most of them use soft copies for a month observation. As per daily log they wrote in a record. These records alone are destructed. Soft copies are retained. Shockingly many students exhibit suicidal tendencies unable to choose career, unable to perform or mismatch between parents expectations and student will. Such records are kept permanently. 90% of them use more than one method of record keeping.

Richard T. Lapan, Sara A. Whitcomb and Nancy M. Aleman (2012), in their study Connecticut Professional School Counselors: College and Career Counseling Services and Smaller Ratios Benefit Students studied career counselling services and their benefit to students. The purpose of the research is to evaluate how far Connecticut school counselling program is helping students. It can be their attendance, retaining in schools, progress, academic scores, discipline, etc. Guidance given along all these lines is important. School counsellors and principals are surveyed on implementation of comprehensive school counselling program. Major questions studied are how do principals perceive counsellor's role? How are they interacting? Are they allotting room and necessary things to counsellors? How far smaller student to counsellor's ratio help in achieving good performance in students? How counsellors are getting occupied?

How far they are answering career choices, social, emotional needs in career counselling services? Questionnaire was sent to 96 schools; these schools' performance was recorded from Connecticut education department website. 72 counsellors, 35 principals responded. Students' outcomes are studied as yearly suspension rates, total actions taken on disciplinary grounds, average daily attendance, high school graduation rates. Researchers also collected data regarding student to counsellor ratio and services rendered by career counsellors. They found that high schools which have higher student to counsellor's ratio are performing well, means lower disciplinary actions, lower drop out, more number of students with good achievement. Counsellors can spend more time, but in many cases their student load is heavy which is educing personal connections.

Mamtha Rani (2016), in her study Design and Implementation of Web-Based Career Stream Assessment System for High School Students, developed a new tool for career counselling. She designed, devolped, evaluated and validated Career and Stream Assessment tools. She selected a sample of 300 students for this. Noted their career clarity pretest and posttest. Found out that these tools are effective in aiding students.

Ranjitauniyal (2021) in her study 'Guidance needs of senior secondary students in relation to their self-confidence and career conflict' studied high school students guidance needs. She has chosen self-confidence and career conflict as independent variables and guidance needs as dependant variable. Diseases caused due to anxiety and depression are more prevelant in adolescents. Also, in large number of suicide cases in adolescents' reason is lack of self-confidence. This became the need of her study. This study is significant to improve self confidence in facing globalised industrial world and how guidance can show them right path of education and career. School students of different schools studying in 11th and 12th grades of Dehradun district in Uttarakhand were selected for this study. Her main objectives were to identify guidance needs, assess self-confidence and career conflict among senior secondary students. Her other objectives include comparing male and female, science and non-science, government and non-government students on this self-confidence, career conflict, guidance needs. Then to bring a relationship between guidance needs and career conflict. The study was confined to 1350 students' of 2017 batch. Descriptive survey method was used. Stratified random sampling was used. After receiving permission from officials for certain schools, simple lottery method was used and 6 blocks were selected in one district. To get the data on guidance needs standard tools were used. They were -1. Guidance needs inventory by Grewal, Likert scale of 4,3,2,1, 0 was used. 2. Self-confidence inventory by Dr. Rekha Gupta. 3. Career conflict scale by Dr. Aneetkumar. 3 questionnaires were given and time limit of 25 mins each was given. Mean, standard deviation, kurtosis was used to reject null hypothesis and prove the point of research. Data collected was compared on different variables as said above. Normality, skewness, etc were obtained. She found that female and non-science, government school students need more vocational career guidance than their counterparts. These students also have lesser self-confidence and hence more guidance needs. But these schools doesn't have full time counsellor which is immediately needed.

RESEARCH GAP

There are no experimental studies nor empirical analysis in the state of Andhra Pradesh. There are very few cases study-based analysis in India. Also, to evaluate effectiveness of these tools there are no studies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Lack of complete awareness, unwilling attitude towards Career Counseling in top management and teachers is the present problem. In India, except some metros it did not enter into all cities and towns. No scope of such awareness in villages.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Is there career counseling in Intermediate colleges?
- Are the college correspondents, lecturers, students aware of it?
- What sort of career decision difficulties are being faced by students?
- If career counselors conduct sessions, will, students benefit from them?
- How far psychometric tests yield accurate results?
- What sort of guidance is being given? Is it only academic? Is there any vocational guidance/ Personality development guidance/ Intra and inter personal issues guidance/ Clinical guidance?
- How far students are facing stress issues in career choices?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To ascertain the effectiveness of tools used in career counseling.
2. To determine how far psychometric tests are mirroring students.
3. To know how far these techniques and career counseling sessions guide students towards 100% clarity.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- H₀1: There is no significant effect of Career Counseling program among students in pretest and posttest.
- H₀2: Psychometric tests are not effective in addressing student career indecisions pretest and posttest.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Present study is an empirical analysis and Data was collected from both Primary and secondary sources. It is also exploratory in nature. An exploratory study entails adopting a range of appropriate ways to obtain new perspectives and develop relevant hypotheses.

(Hair et al., 2017) claimed exploratory research is important to producing new concepts and knowledge on possible scale development throughout the following phase of descriptive research. Convenience sampling was used. 321 students are selected from Intermediate colleges.

Group guidance is provided for students. Then Career decision making difficulties questionnaire was given. After those psychometric tools are used. These tests are for career and stream selection. They generate a report. Basing on that, sessions are taken. Posttests, same questionnaire that was given pretest was given.

Data Collection Tools

To gather reliable information, data has been collected both in online and offline form. A structured questionnaires of three types were used to collect data from top management, teachers and students.

Data Analysis

Quantitative analysis was done in SPSS. Reports of tests are analysed.

This is a sample career report which shows 6 broad areas and students raking in each, correspondingly codes are also generated.

You are **70%** Realistic. (Doers)

Realistic people are practical, athletic, mechanically inclined, nature lovers and concrete. They like to "do" things such as playing a sport, work outdoors, tinkering with machines/vehicles, tend or train animals, operate tools and machines or read a blueprint. They are hands-on type of people.

Major features of Realistic people are:

- Like to work with their hands and focus on things in the physical world & use physical skills.
- Like to repair and work with tools, machines, or animals; outdoor work is often preferred.
- Prefer problems that are concrete rather than abstract; want practical solutions that can be acted out.
- Characteristics include stable, assertive, physical strength, practical.

Suitable Careers:

- Forester
- Wildlife Manager
- Auto Mechanic
- Drafter
- Engineer
- Manufacturing Worker
- Dental Lab Technician
- Quality Control Inspector

Sample Academic Majors:

- Administrative of Justice
- Physical Education
- Medical Technology
- Engineering
- Agriculture
- Architecture

Pretest questionnaire and posttest analysis has been done using t test.

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	pre test	post test
Mean	24.6	61.4
Variance	149.8	124.8
Observations	54	54
Pearson Correlation	0.877277625	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	-13.96908897	
P(T<=t) one-tail	7.6165E-05	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00015233	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

Since P is less than 0.05, null hypothesis is being rejected.

Hence psychometric tests are effective in addressing difficulties during career decision process.

CONCLUSION

There are various reasons for difficulties in making career decisions. They are lack of complete information regarding courses and colleges, internal conflicts with parents, financial problems, not knowing themselves properly. When they are in confusion regarding career, career selection test worked best. Stream selector test guided to select correct streams. 16pf guided students to know their personality as well as best matched career roles. 99 % the students are happy with the career counseling session and are ready to take up the courses as per the reports given by above tests. 48.5% of the students expressed mismatch between parents' wishes and their interests and are ready to take help of career counsellor mediation with parents. These psychometric tests acted as good tools to assist students in career counseling.

SUGGESTIONS

Psychometric tests aid career counselors. These tests can be conducted online. So, they are beneficial not only in cities but also in villages. So far, such services are available only in metros. But since these tests and sessions can be done online, it will benefit rural India at large. Student can produce the best results if such career counseling is done and is guided to take up what they like and what they are skilled at.

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